

MICRO-MECHANICAL MODELING OF FLOW THROUGH RANDOMLY PACKED BEDS OF CYLINDERS & SPHERES: DISPERSION, DEFORMATION AND HEAT TRANSFER

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1 Introduction

This presentation indirectly summarizes the contacts between Luleå university of technology and University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign and Professor Scott White on composites manufacturing. The collaboration was initiated by Professor Rikard Gebart (then also at SICOMP) and Professor Charles Tucker III during the 90s and has then continued.

Having this in-mind the presentation will focus on previously published technical results on the flow through random arrays of cylinders and beds of spheres. The cylinders are parallel and straight and may mimic fibres in fibre bundles during liquid moulding processes, for instance. The main method used is numerical modelling based on Delaunay triangulation and Voronoi diagram, see Figure 1, [1], and the quantities of interest are dispersion, deformation and heat and mass transfer. The numerical results are verified and validated with numerical and experimental results from the literature.

2 Theory

The detailed flow field for low Reynolds number flow through random packings of cylinders and spheres is derived. The number of particles is several thousands and the porosities ranges between 0.4 and 0.6. The system of particles is divided into smaller volumes with Voronoi diagrams and the flow field is obtained by usage of the single and dual stream function. The local saturated flow fields are approximated as for close packed particles and the overall flow pattern is obtained by minimising the dissipation rate of energy [1].

Figure 1. Example of Voronoi diagrams, blue lines. The green areas are the fibres.

3 Dispersion

The longitudinal (DL) and transverse (DT) dispersion coefficients are computed by fitting the resulting effluent curve to a 1-D solution of a continuous model and by fitting the numerical concentration profile to an approximate 2-D solution, respectively. The obtained values of DL and DT are in agreement with 3-D experimental data from the literature enabling a study of the effects of pore structure and porosity on DL and DT [2-4].

4 Deformation

Flow induced alterations of permeability is studied. The change of permeability is obtained for elastic deformations of the positions of the cylinders and the

spheres using either of two methods. Each particle is elastically attached to single points or the particles are connected via an elastic porous network. The results show that the permeability for large random systems increases as a function of velocity and thus the deformation. The alteration is, however, much less for 2-D cases like parallel cylinders than for spheres. The relative increase in permeability becomes larger as the porosity increases from 0.4 to 0.6 [1,5-6]. In addition particle deposition during impregnation of dual-scale fabrics is modelled with qualitative agreement to experiments [7-9].

5 Heat and mass transfer

Finally the model is applied to heat and mass transfer. To exemplify, simulations of drying yields show variation in the distribution of temperature and moisture content in the final phase of drying [10-12].

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7 References

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